
Analytical Modeling of a Proton Recoil Telescope

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12 13 **Abstract**

14 Neutron spectrometry in fusion diagnostics requires precise knowledge of the Proton Recoil Telescope (PRT)
15 response functions. We present a comprehensive analytical model, extending a lesser-known approach
16 (published in German) [1], that computes response functions and detection efficiencies for a wide range of
17 geometrical configurations, including extended, off-axis, and asymmetric neutron sources. The model
18 successfully recovers Gotoh's integral formulation [2] for axially symmetric, thin-radiator configurations with
19 parallel beams, validating our broader framework. We derive, for the first time, a closed-form analytical
20 solution for the equal-radius, on-axis geometry with proton energy loss using elliptic integrals. This result
21 eliminates the need for numerical integration of Gotoh's equations and provides immediate computational
22 access to exact response functions. Asymptotic approximations for varying source-detector distances yield
23 simplified expressions suitable for practical visualization and rapid system optimization. The framework
24 incorporates proton energy loss through Bragg-Kleeman range-energy relations in flat, uniform radiator
25 surfaces and has been validated against full numerical integration. This analytical approach enables efficient
26 calculation of response functions for any combination of source geometry, radiator configuration, and detector
27 arrangement, offering computational advantages that are several orders of magnitude faster than Monte Carlo
28 simulations and making it particularly valuable for iterative experimental design optimization and real-time
29 diagnostic applications.

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31 **Keywords:** Proton recoil telescope; Neutron spectrometry; Response function; Elliptic integrals; Bragg-
32 Kleeman; Fusion diagnostics

33 34 **1. Introduction**

35 The history of the PRT dates back to the earliest studies of neutron-proton scattering, where G. Bernardini and
36 F. Oppenheimer first established the technique of observing recoil protons in coincidence (see [3]). The
37 foundational geometric formalisms for calculating the detection efficiency and response function were
38 subsequently developed by [4], [5], [6], [7],[2], [8] among the many, establishing the initial integral equations
39 to correlate kinematics with the detector's solid angle and incorporating efficiency and correction factors, or
40 also computer table calculations. Precise modeling of the geometry remains central, as exemplified by methods
41 such as the Bessel-function expansion derived for parallel-disk systems [9]. The correct application of

42 kinematic transformations, notably the critical requirement for full relativistic correction [10], [11]. A
 43 secondary yet crucial component is the accurate modeling of proton energy loss within the radiator and
 44 detector, using principles such as the Bethe-Bloch and Bragg-Kleeman rules [12]. This necessity for detailed
 45 physical modeling, including the minimization of range uncertainties [13], [14], [15] and the ongoing
 46 refinement of these kinematic and geometric tools is essential for modern PRT applications in dosimetry and
 47 solid-state detection, for example, the design and validation of a PRT using a silicon detector and Monte Carlo
 48 simulations, [16],[17] Recoil protons can be proficiently used in neutron spectrometry. In this case, the
 49 measured energy spectrum $P_E(E) = \frac{dP}{dE}$ (where P is the number of protons ejected in a hydrogen-containing
 50 body, the radiator, by fast neutrons and detected in a detector) and the unknown neutron spectrum
 51 $N_E(E) = \frac{dN}{dE}$ (where N is the number of neutrons emitted from a source) are related by the following integral
 52 equation:

$$P_E(E) = \int n(E, E') N_E(E') dE' \quad (1)$$

54 where $n(E, E')$ is the response function kernel required to solve this integral equation. The response function
 55 critically depends on the measurement geometry, proton energy loss in the radiator, and the characteristics of
 56 the neutron source. While monochromatic neutron calibration is theoretically possible, it is often impractical
 57 for weak, extended sources requiring optimized geometries with small source-detector distances and thick
 58 radiators. Under these conditions, off-axis neutron collisions and significant proton deceleration create the
 59 characteristic "shark fin" response shape, necessitating computational determination of the response function.
 60 Previous work has addressed idealized cases with point sources, axial symmetry, and "good geometry"
 61 assumptions. This paper presents a comprehensive computational approach for general source geometries,
 62 radiator shapes, and detector arrangements. The method accommodates flat foil radiators of uniform thickness,
 63 flat detector surfaces, and angled configurations that enable source shielding. The calculated response function
 64 provides the detection efficiency—the probability of registering a proton per emitted neutron of energy E_0 —
 65 for any specified measurement geometry.

66 The present work focuses on the geometric and kinematic aspects of the PRT response function under well-
 67 defined physical assumptions. Effects such as detector segmentation, electronic response, background
 68 contributions, and secondary nuclear reactions, while important for complete system characterization, are
 69 beyond the scope of this analytical treatment and are typically addressed through complementary Monte Carlo
 70 simulations. The analytical framework presented here is intended to complement, rather than replace, full
 71 Monte Carlo simulations, providing rapid evaluation of response functions for design optimization and serving
 72 as a benchmark for numerical methods.

73 The formulation presented in Sections 2–5 builds upon the general framework originally developed in [1] and
 74 the integral formalism of [2]. We adopt the final expressions for the response function and efficiency directly
 75 from these references, reproducing only the key results needed to establish notation and to make the subsequent
 76 novel derivations self-contained. The reader is referred to [1] (originally published in German) and [2] for the
 77 complete intermediate derivations. The new contributions of this work—namely, the closed-form analytical
 78 solution in terms of elliptic integrals (Section 8), the independent Geant4 validation (Section 7), and the
 79 systematic treatment of proton energy loss via Bragg-Kleeman relations—are direct extensions of these
 80 classical results.

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82 2. Mathematical Formulation of the Response Function and Detection Efficiency

83 The response function $n(E, E_0)$ represents the proton spectrum normalized to one emitted neutron for
 84 monochromatic neutrons of energy E_0 . With $N_E(E') = \delta(E' - E_0)$, Eq. (1) yields $P_E(E) = n(E, E_0)$. The detection
 85 efficiency ε is:

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$$\varepsilon(E_0) = \int n(E, E_0) dE \quad (2)$$

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For an extended source with normalized density distribution $q(\mathbf{r}')$ emitting monochromatic neutrons of energy E_0 , the normalized differential neutron flux density at a point \mathbf{r} on the radiator in a direction ω_1 can be expressed as an integral over the source volume that combines the inverse-square law, the source density distribution, and directionality (see [1], Eqs. 1–4 for the full derivation). This yields the quantity $\phi'(\mathbf{r}, \omega_1)$, which enters the response function calculation as the weight for neutron contributions from all source points.

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Fig. 1 Conceptual schema for the converter foil limited by the two drawn planes

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The neutrons incident from the source, with the normalized differential flux density $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, \omega_1)$, $[\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}(P)]$, onto a flat hydrogen-containing radiator foil of thickness h at point P , release recoil protons along the path \overline{PB} of length $l = h / \cos \gamma_1$ (see Fig. 1), where $\gamma_1 \ll (\omega_1, \mathbf{n})$, \mathbf{n} is the unit vector normal to the foil. We assume that the thickness of the foil (more properly the density thickness τ_0 expressed in mg/cm^2) is present, but so small that the neutron beam along \overline{PB} is not significantly slowed down and at most one proton is knocked out per neutron. τ_0 is also negligible compared to all other lengths that occur. The normalized production area density on the foil surface for the recoil protons formed along \overline{PB} with constant density in the direction ω_2 , is $\Psi n h \sigma_\omega$ where n is the number density of hydrogen nuclei in the foil and $\sigma_\omega(\omega_2) = \sigma_\omega(E_n, \mathcal{G})$ is the differential cross-section in the center-of-mass system with $\mathcal{G} \ll (\omega_1, \omega_2)$. The initial energy of the protons is $E_{p1} = E_n \cos^2 \mathcal{G}$. The protons traverse within the foil in the ω_2 direction, over the distances x ($0 \leq x \leq z$), and, in addition to a small, negligible angular deflection, suffer an energy loss. Hence, it's useful to introduce a range $R(E)$ whose first derivative can be expressed as:

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$$\left. \frac{dR(E)}{dE} \right|_{E=E_p} = h \cdot f(E_p) \quad (3)$$

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where the function $f(E)$ is related to the energy loss of protons as they traverse the radiator foil. Specifically, it is derived from the Bragg-Kleeman range-energy relation, which describes how a proton's range in a material depends on its energy E . Now, the probability density for the exit energy E of the $n h \sigma_\omega(\omega_2)$ recoil protons, is:

$$W(E | \boldsymbol{\omega}_1, \boldsymbol{\omega}_2) = \begin{cases} \frac{h}{z} f(E) & (E_2 \leq E \leq E_1) \\ 0 & \text{otherw.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

111
112 W depends on $E_{1,2}$ via $\boldsymbol{\omega}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_2$. If $E_2 = 0$, W is generally not normalized to one, as not all protons leave the
113 foil. Now, we neglect proton energy loss along their flight path between the converter and the detector,
114 assuming a vacuum. Furthermore, we assume that every proton hitting the detector's surface is also registered
115 and that its energy is measured accurately. By integrating W with the weight $n h \sigma_{\omega}(\omega_2)$ over all possible
116 directions $\boldsymbol{\omega}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_2$, we obtain the response function over the converter surfaces ($d\mathbf{r}$ is the area element
117 identified by \mathbf{r}).

$$n(E, E_0) = n h \int_{G_1} W(E | \boldsymbol{\omega}_1, \boldsymbol{\omega}_2) \Psi(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}_1) \sigma_{\omega}(\omega_2) d\boldsymbol{\omega}_1 d\boldsymbol{\omega}_2 d\mathbf{r} \quad (5)$$

119 and for the efficiency

$$\varepsilon(E_0) = n h \int_{G_2} \Psi(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}_1) \sigma_{\omega}(\omega_2) d\boldsymbol{\omega}_1 d\boldsymbol{\omega}_2 d\mathbf{r} \quad (6)$$

121 The information contained in W in Eq. (5), on the energy distribution of the detected protons, is implicitly
122 included in the integration of Eq. (6) through G_2 , where we are only interested in the detection probability,
123 rather than the specific energy distribution of the detected proton. In the energy range around $E_0 \leq 10$ MeV,
124 if (n, p) scattering is isotropic in the center-of-mass system, then the following applies with the total cross
125 section $\sigma(E_n)$.

$$\sigma_{\omega}(\omega_2) = \frac{1}{\pi} \sigma_0(E_0) \cos \vartheta \quad (\cos \vartheta \geq 0) \quad (7)$$

127 We restrict ourselves to this energy range, which is interesting in the spectrometry of neutron sources.
128 However, the specific form of the function $\sigma_{\omega}(\omega_2)$ is not critical for what follows; from Eq. (5) and (6), with
129 Eqs.(3), (4) and (7), we now obtain:

$$n(E, E_0) = \frac{n h}{(2\pi)^2} \sigma_0(E_0) f(E) \cdot \int_{G_1} q(\mathbf{r} - \lambda \boldsymbol{\omega}_1) \cos \vartheta \cos(\gamma_2) d\lambda d\boldsymbol{\omega}_1 d\boldsymbol{\omega}_2 d\mathbf{r} \quad (8)$$

132 Now, following Eq. (2), the total efficiency $\varepsilon(E_0)$ is defined by integrating the response function over all
133 possible exit energies $\varepsilon(E_0) = \int n(E, E_0) dE$, hence:

$$\varepsilon(E_0) = \frac{n h}{(2\pi)^2} \sigma_0(E_0) \cdot \int_{G_2} q(\mathbf{r} - \lambda \boldsymbol{\omega}_1) \cos \vartheta d\lambda d\boldsymbol{\omega}_1 d\boldsymbol{\omega}_2 d\mathbf{r} \quad (9)$$

135 The sevenfold integration in equations (8) and (9) arises from the need to integrate over all relevant variables
136 that determine the PRT's response function. The integration regions $G_{1,2}$ of these sevenfold integrals are
137 determined by the radiator surface and source volume, and by the condition that the ray in the direction $\boldsymbol{\omega}_2$
138 must strike the front surface of the detector and that σ_{ω} is positive, i.e., with the azimuthal angles β_1 and β_2 of
139 $\boldsymbol{\omega}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega}_2$, respectively, relative to the axis \mathbf{n} . The integral over G_2 in Eq. (9) depends only on the geometry,
140 so that

$$\varepsilon(E_0) = n h \sigma_0(E_0) \cdot \chi \quad (10)$$

142 with \mathcal{Z} dimensionless. It holds that $\mathbf{n}(E_0, E_0) = \mathbf{0}$, because the integrand in Eq. (8) is bounded, and the
 143 condition $E_2 \leq E \leq E_1$ for $E = E_0$ is only fulfilled on the hypersurface $\boldsymbol{\omega}_1 = \boldsymbol{\omega}_2$; i.e., $\mathcal{G} = 0$. Formulas (9) and
 144 (10) for the efficiency ε , are only valid as long as all protons can leave the foil, i.e., a lower limit $E_{\min} > 0$ exists
 145 for all possible E_2 of the region G_2 . Otherwise, ε must be determined from Eq. (2). Below E_{\min} , the response
 146 function vanishes.

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148 3. Energy Dependence of the Response Function and the 'Shark Fin' Phenomenon

149 The derivative of n with respect to E reveals the characteristic 'shark fin' shape of the response function. Using
 150 the Heaviside function H , we can include the energy bounds $E_2 \leq E \leq E_1$ into Eq. (8):

$$151 \quad n(E, E_0) = \frac{n h}{(2\pi)^2} \sigma_0(E_0) f(E) \cdot \int_{G_2} H(E_1 - E) H(E - E_2) q(\mathbf{r} - \lambda \boldsymbol{\omega}_1) \cos \mathcal{G} \cos \gamma_2 d\lambda d\boldsymbol{\omega}_1 d\boldsymbol{\omega}_2 d\mathbf{r} \quad (11)$$

152 It can be proved, see [1], the following important relationship

$$153 \quad \frac{\partial \{n(E, E_0)/f(E)\}}{\partial E} = -n_0(E, E_0) \quad (E_2^* \leq E \leq E_0) \quad (12)$$

154 Eq. (12) is a differential equation linking the real response function $n(E, E_0)$ —which includes energy loss—
 155 to the idealized, purely geometric response $n_0(E, E_0)$. It shows that the ideal response determines the rate of
 156 change of the real response, but with a negative sign. Integrating Eq. (12), yields the solution:

$$157 \quad n(E, E_0) = f(E) \cdot \int_E^{E_0} n_0(E', E_0) dE'$$

158 where $f(E)$ from Eq. (3), is related to the proton range function, and the integral represents the cumulative
 159 probability of detecting a proton with energy $\geq E$ in an ideal, lossless scenario. This integral peaks at low E
 160 and drops to zero as E approaches E_0 , explaining the characteristic "**shark fin**" shape of the response function:

- 161 • The rising edge is shaped by $f(E)$ and the slowly decreasing integral of n_0 .
- 162 • The sharp drop-off at high energy occurs as the integral rapidly vanishes near E_0 .

163 When $n_0(E, E_0) = 0$, $n(E, E_0)$ becomes proportional to $f(E)$, proving that the "**plateau**" of the response function
 164 directly reflects the material's stopping power characteristics—a key consequence of proton deceleration.

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166 4. Geometric Model: Coordinate Systems and Measurement Setup

167 We use Weise's general approach and notation for the calculation of the integrals in Eqs. (8) and (9). The
 168 geometric relationships are shown in Fig. 2.

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Fig. 2 Illustrative sketch of the coordinate systems and measurement setup

- The coordinate system origin O is placed at the radiator foil plane.
- The Z -axis is perpendicular to the foil, pointing toward the detector.
- The X -axis is aligned with the intersection line of the radiator and detector planes (if not parallel).
- The smallest possible circle of radius R encloses the radiator surface.
- The neutron source is enclosed by the smallest possible sphere of radius R_1 , centered at M_1
- The detector surface is enclosed by the smallest possible sphere of radius R_2 , centered at M_2 .
- The detector plane is inclined at an angle α relative to the radiator plane.
- The angles Ψ_1 and Ψ_2 define the maximum detectable neutron and proton directions, respectively.

5. Analysis of Response Function Behavior and Geometric Effects

182 Fig. 3 Top panel: family of response functions $n(E, E_0)$ for neutron energies E_0 from 1 to 20 MeV in 1 MeV steps, showing the
 183 characteristic “shark fin” shape and its evolution with increasing neutron energy for the geometry described in the text. Bottom panel:
 184 detailed representation of the response function $n(E, E_0)$ from the text example. n_0 is the purely geometric response function for $E_0 =$
 185 3 MeV; n_1 is the response function with “good” geometry and a point source for $E_0 = 3$ MeV

186 Fig. 3 shows, as an example, the response function $n(E, E_0)$ obtained using the method described above with
 187 the following values: the numerical evaluation of the response function was performed using for the
 188 polyethylene density $\rho = 0.94$ g/cm³ (from NIST), a polyethylene alpha value of $\alpha_p = 1.85321 \times 10^{-3}$, Bragg–
 189 Kleeman exponent $a = 1.80173$ (both from NIST data best fit, see Fig. 4), used in the range-energy relation of
 190 protons in polyethylene with the formula $R(E) = \rho \cdot \alpha_p \cdot E^a$, and foil density thickness $\tau_0 = 8.9 \times 10^{-3}$ g/cm²,
 191 from [1] ch. 4. For the geometry, $r_1 = 0.83$ cm and $r_2 = 0.796$ cm were assumed for the characteristic radii
 192 (ibid.). Furthermore, the source and detector positions were set to $X_{M1} = Y_{M1} = X'_{M2} = Y'_{M2} = \alpha = 0$, with Z_{M1}
 193 $= -5.0$ cm and $Z_T = 8.3$ cm (ibid.). These values were used in the integration routine to obtain the plotted
 194 response functions.

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Fig. 4 Best fit for the Bragg-Kleeman range energy relation in the range 0-20 MeV. The best fit data for alpha is $\alpha_P = 1.85321 \times 10^{-3}$ and for the exponent is $a = 1.80173$

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For the total cross section $\sigma_0(E_0)$, the Gammel formula, as given in [18], was used. The source density was assumed constant over the source volume V , i.e., $q = 1/V$.

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Fig. 5 Behavior of the characteristic energy values for the response function of the example in the text. The crossover between E_1^* and E_2^* occurs at E_0 approximately 11.06 MeV, while the intersection point between \hat{E} and E_2^* takes place at E_0 around 11.7 MeV, and the relative minimum of $E_{max} - E_{min}$ occurs at $E_0 \sim 10.3$ MeV

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- The response function $n(E, E_0)$ at constant neutron energy E_0 (Fig. 3) shows typical behavior, with characteristic energies (Fig. 5) $E_{max}=E_0$ and E_{min} .

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- E_2^* marks the sharp maximum or steep drop-off in the response curve, aligning with the plateau caused by proton deceleration.

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- The energy \hat{E} represents the rounded maximum of the response function, transitioning to E_2^* at $E_0 \approx 11.06$ MeV.

- 210 • For $E_0 < 3.0$ MeV, $E_2^* < E_1^*$, and n is proportional to $f(E)$ in the range $E_2^* \leq E \leq E_1^*$, reflecting a "good
- 211 geometry" scenario.
- 212 • The total width $E_{\max} - E_{\min}$ of the response function is minimized at $E_0 \approx 10.3$ MeV.
- 213 • The full width at half maximum (FWHM) reaches a relative minimum at $E_0 \approx 18.9$ MeV.
- 214 • At higher E_0 , the width increases due to the geometric response function n_0 , which scales with E_0 .
- 215 • At lower E_0 , deceleration effects broaden the response, but the width remains below E_0 , causing the
- 216 FWHM to decrease toward zero for $E_0 < 2.7$ MeV.

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218 **6. Extension and validation of Gotoh's integral formalism**

219 In the energy range around $E_n \leq 10$ MeV, if (n, p) scattering is isotropic in the center-of-mass system, then

220 the following applies with the total cross section $\sigma(E_n)$.

221
$$\sigma_{\omega}(\omega_2) = \frac{1}{\pi} \sigma(E_n) \cos \mathcal{G} \quad (\cos \mathcal{G} \geq 0) \quad (13)$$

222 We restrict ourselves to this energy range, which is interesting in the spectrometry of neutron sources.

223 However, the specific form of the function $\sigma_{\omega}(\omega_2)$ is not critical for what follows; from Eq. (5) we have:

224
$$n(E, E_0) = \int W(E | \omega_1, \omega_2) \Psi(\mathbf{r}, \omega_1) n \tau_0 \sigma_{\omega}(\omega_2) d\omega_1 d\omega_2 d\mathbf{r}; \quad (14)$$

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226

227 *Fig. 6 A PRT with a converter of finite thickness*

228 For a parallel neutron beam incident perpendicular to the foil surface:

- 229 • The flux $\Psi(\mathbf{r}, \omega_1)$ becomes constant = N (neutrons per unit area)
- 230 • The direction ω_1 is fixed (perpendicular to the surface)
- 231 • $\gamma_1 = 0$, so $\cos \gamma_1 = 1$

232 • The integral over $d\omega_1$ disappears since the direction is fixed

233 • From Eq. (4), $W(E | \omega_1, \omega_2) = \frac{\tau_0}{z} f(E)$

234 Hence:

$$\begin{aligned}
 n(E_p, E_n) &= n N \tau_0 \int_{G_1} \frac{\tau_0}{z} f(E_p) \frac{1}{\pi} \sigma(E_n) \cos \vartheta d\omega_2 d\Omega = \\
 &= \frac{n N}{\pi} \cdot \left. \frac{dR(E)}{dE} \right|_{E=E_p} \cdot \sigma(E_n) \cdot \int_{G_1} \cos^2 \vartheta d\omega_2 d\Omega
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

236 Here, as already stated, we consider the impinging neutrons perpendicularly to the surface, and integrating ω_2
 237 on the half-space, we have

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$$\boxed{n(E_p, E_n) = 2n N \cdot \sigma(E_n) \cdot \left. \frac{dR(E)}{dE} \right|_{E=E_p} \cdot \int_{G_1} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta d\vartheta d\phi} \tag{16}$$

240 This equation is a generalization of Eq. (36) of [2] (where a multiplication factor $f(\vartheta)$ appears as well as the
 241 integration limits since, differently from G_1 , the converter and detector in Gotoh's paper are already considered
 242 of a particular geometry shape). Analogously, for the efficiency, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varepsilon(E_n) &= \int \Psi(\mathbf{r}, \omega_1) n \tau_0 \sigma_\omega(\omega_2) d\omega_1 d\omega_2 d\mathbf{r} = \\
 &= N \tau_0 \sigma(E_n) \cdot \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{G_2} \cos \vartheta d\omega_2 d\Omega
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

244 The integration regions $G_{1,2}$ of these sevenfold integrals are determined by the converter surface, the source
 245 volume, and by the condition that the ray in the direction ω_2 must strike the front surface of the detector and
 246 that σ_ω is positive. For G_1 , it is further required, according to Eq. (4), that for fixed E , the inequality
 247 $E_{p2} \leq E \leq E_{p1}$ is satisfied. The integral in Eq. (17) depends only on the geometry, so that we can set

$$\boxed{\varepsilon(E_n) = N \tau_0 \sigma(E_n) \cdot \varkappa} \tag{18}$$

249 with \varkappa dimensionless. It holds that $n(E_n, E_n) = 0$ because of the integrand in Eq. (5) is bounded and the
 250 condition $E_{p2} \leq E \leq E_{p1}$ for $E = E_n$ is only fulfilled on the hypersurface $\omega_1 = \omega_2$; i.e., $\vartheta = 0$. The preceding
 251 formulas are only valid as long as the protons can leave the foil, hence a lower limit $E_{\min} > 0$ exists for all
 252 possible E_{p2} of the region G_2 . Below E_{\min} , the response function vanishes.

253

254 7. Special Case: On-Axis Cylindrical Converter and Disk Detector

255 In this section, we'll specialize the preceding results for an on-axis cylindrical converter and a disk detector.

256 In this case, the G_1 integration domain of Eq. (16) is given by the following set of simultaneous inequalities:

$$\begin{aligned}
& 0 \leq r \leq r_1 \\
& -\pi \leq \psi < \pi \\
& 0 \leq \tau \leq \tau_0 \\
257 \quad & 0 \leq \vartheta < \pi/2 \\
& -\pi \leq \phi < \pi \\
& E_p \leq E_n \\
& 0 \leq q \leq r_2
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

258 Anyway, the number of independent variables is five, not seven, because we can establish the following two
259 relationships. For the first relationship, we observe that the proton's initial energy, E_{p1} , is given by
260 $E_{p1} = E_n \cos^2 \vartheta$ and the total range of the proton with initial energy E_{p1} can be expressed as the sum of the
261 distance traveled through the foil and the remaining range after exiting $R(E_n \cos^2 \vartheta) = x + R(E)$. We assume
262 now that the thickness of the foil τ_0 is also negligible compared to all other lengths; if the distance x traveled
263 by the proton through the foil can be approximated to the maximum path length z and the angle of incidence ϑ
264 by $z = \frac{\tau_0}{\cos \vartheta}$, we have:

$$265 \quad R(E_n \cos^2 \vartheta) \simeq x + R(E) = \frac{\tau}{\cos \vartheta} + R(E) \tag{20}$$

266 For the second relationship, from Fig. 6, we have:

$$267 \quad q^2 = r^2 + r'^2 - 2 r r' \cos \phi \tag{21}$$

268 where $r' = d \tan \vartheta$. Now we can rewrite the multiple integral that appears in Eq. (16) into a form of repeated
269 integral:

$$270 \quad \int_{G_1} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta d\vartheta d\phi = \int_{\vartheta_{\min}}^{\vartheta_{\max}} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta d\vartheta \int_{r_{\min}(\vartheta)}^{r_{\max}(\vartheta)} r dr \int_{\phi_{\min}(r, \vartheta)}^{\phi_{\max}(r, \vartheta)} d\phi \int_{\psi_{\min}(\phi, r, \vartheta)}^{\psi_{\max}(\phi, r, \vartheta)} d\psi \tag{22}$$

271 By substituting Eqs. (20), (21) and $E = E_p$ into ineqs. (19), the set of simultaneous inequalities defining the G_1
272 integration domain can be contracted to:

$$273 \quad 0 \leq r \leq r_1 \tag{23}$$

$$274 \quad -\pi \leq \psi < \pi \tag{24}$$

$$275 \quad 0 \leq \underbrace{\left[R(E_n \cos^2 \vartheta) - R(E_p) \right]}_{\tau} \cos \vartheta \leq \tau_0 \tag{25}$$

$$276 \quad 0 \leq \vartheta < \pi/2 \tag{26}$$

$$277 \quad -\pi \leq \phi < \pi \tag{27}$$

$$278 \quad 0 \leq \underbrace{r^2 + r'^2 - 2 r r' \cos \phi}_{q^2} \leq r_2^2 \tag{28}$$

279 The variable ψ is constrained only by ineq. (24). Accordingly, the integration limits with respect to ψ are given
280 from the beginning:

281
$$\Psi_{\max}(\phi, r, \vartheta) = -\Psi_{\min}(\phi, r, \vartheta) = \pi$$

282 The constraints on ϕ are ineqs. (27) and (28). When $r = 0$ or $\vartheta = 0$, ineq. (28) does not work as a constraint on
 283 ϕ . Otherwise, r , $\tan \vartheta$, and d are all positive (hence: $0 \leq \vartheta < \pi/2$). To find the constraints on ϕ , we have to
 284 consider two cases: the first case when $r_1 \leq r_2$ (or $r_1 > r_2$) and $r' \leq r_2 - r_1$ (or $r' \leq r_1 - r_2$), second case when
 285 $|r_1 - r_2| < r' \leq r_1 + r_2$. In the first case, there are no intersections between the two circles, in the second case
 286 there are, and we can find the constraints on ϕ (see Fig. 7):

287
 288 *Fig. 7 Finding the constraints on ϕ .* In this case, the origin is placed in P' on the right of O' with the distance $r = O'P'$ with a
 289 negative sign. ϕ_{\max} corresponds to α_{\min} and $\phi_{\max} = -\phi_{\min}$

290 After finding the intersection of the two circles expressed in polar coordinates, the upper and lower integration
 291 limits for ϕ are given by the following two cases:

292
$$\phi_{\max}(r, \vartheta) = -\phi_{\min}(r, \vartheta) = \begin{cases} \pi & \text{for } r_1 \leq r_2 \quad (\text{or } r_1 > r_2) \quad \text{and} \quad r' \leq r_2 - r_1 \quad (\text{or } r' \leq r_1 - r_2) \\ \arccos\left(\frac{r^2 + r'^2 - r_2^2}{2r r'}\right) & \text{for } |r_1 - r_2| < r' \leq r_1 + r_2 \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

293 We now focus on the inequalities involving r , specifically Eqs. (23) and (28). From the first, we obtain:

294
$$r_{\max} = r_1$$

295 From the second:

296
$$r^2 + r'^2 - 2r r' \cos \phi \leq r_2^2$$

297 This is a quadratic inequality in r . To find the constraints on r , we solve the quadratic equation and, considering
 298 Eq. (23), we have:

299
$$\begin{aligned} r_{\min}(\vartheta) &= \max(0, r' - r_2) \\ r_{\max}(\vartheta) &= \min(r_1, r' + r_2) \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

300 The range value for the angle ϑ is

$$301 \quad 0 \leq \vartheta \leq \arctan \frac{r_1 + r_2}{d} \quad (31)$$

302 The condition from Eq. (25) determines the lower limit on ϑ :

$$303 \quad R(E_n \cos^2 \vartheta) \leq R(E_p) + \frac{\tau_0}{\cos \vartheta} \quad (32)$$

304 The smallest ϑ that satisfies this inequality is ϑ_{\min} . If we denote with $\tau_3 = R(E_n) - R(E_p)$, we have that:

$$305 \quad \bullet \text{ if } \tau_3 \leq \tau_0 \Rightarrow \vartheta_{\min} = 0$$

$$306 \quad \bullet \text{ if } \tau_3 > \tau_0 \Rightarrow \vartheta_{\min} = \vartheta_3 \text{ where } \vartheta_3 \text{ is the solution of } R(E_n \cos^2 \vartheta_3) = R(E_p) + \frac{\tau_0}{\cos \vartheta_3}.$$

307 The upper limit ϑ_{\max} is determined by the condition Eq. (25) and Eq. (31):

$$308 \quad \bullet \text{ if } \vartheta_1 \leq \vartheta_2 \quad \text{where } \vartheta_1 = \arctan \left(\frac{r_1 + r_2}{d} \right) \text{ and } \vartheta_2 = \arccos \sqrt{\frac{E_p}{E_n}} \Rightarrow \vartheta_{\max} = \vartheta_1$$

$$309 \quad \bullet \text{ if } \vartheta_1 > \vartheta_2 \Rightarrow \vartheta_{\max} = \vartheta_2$$

310 Hence:

$$311 \quad \vartheta_{\max} = \begin{cases} \vartheta_1 & \text{for } \vartheta_1 \leq \vartheta_2 \\ \vartheta_2 & \text{for } \vartheta_1 > \vartheta_2 \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

$$\vartheta_{\min} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } \tau_3 \leq \tau_0 \\ \vartheta_3 & \text{for } \tau_3 > \tau_0 \end{cases}$$

312 Now, we are in the position to perform the repeated integral of Eq. (22) and considering only the forward half-
313 space, we have:

$$314 \quad \int_{G_1} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta d\vartheta r dr d\phi d\psi = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\vartheta_{\min}}^{\vartheta_{\max}} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta d\vartheta \int_{r_{\min}(\vartheta)}^{r_{\max}(\vartheta)} r dr \int_{\phi_{\min}(r,\vartheta)}^{\phi_{\max}(r,\vartheta)} d\phi \underbrace{\int_{\psi_{\min}(\phi,r,\vartheta)}^{\psi_{\max}(\phi,r,\vartheta)} d\psi}_{2\pi} \quad (34)$$

315 Using Eq. (29) we have to distinguish two cases:

$$316 \quad \int_{\phi_{\min}(r,\vartheta)}^{\phi_{\max}(r,\vartheta)} d\phi = \begin{cases} 2\pi & \text{for } r_1 \leq r_2 \quad (\text{or } r_1 > r_2) \\ & \text{and } r' \leq r_2 - r_1 \quad (\text{or } r' \leq r_1 - r_2) \\ 2 \arccos \left(\frac{r^2 + r'^2 - r_2^2}{2 r r'} \right) & \text{for } |r_1 - r_2| < r' \leq r_1 + r_2 \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

317 Hence, performing now the integration on r , and splitting the integration range in two parts, we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_{G_1} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta d\vartheta r dr d\phi d\psi = \\
318 \quad & = \int_{\vartheta_{\min}}^{\vartheta_{\max}} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta \cdot \left[\int_{r_{\min}(\vartheta)}^{r_{\max}(\vartheta)} 2\pi r dr \quad \text{or} \quad \int_{r_{\min}(\vartheta)}^{r_{\max}(\vartheta)} 2r \arccos\left(\frac{r^2 + r'^2 - r_2^2}{2r r'}\right) dr \right] d\vartheta = \\
& = \int_{\vartheta_{\min}}^{\vartheta_{\max}} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta \cdot \left[\underbrace{f_1(\vartheta)}_{f_1(\vartheta)} \quad \text{or} \quad \underbrace{f_2(\vartheta)}_{f_2(\vartheta)} \right] d\vartheta = \int_{\vartheta_{\min}}^{\vartheta_{\max}} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta \cdot f(\vartheta) d\vartheta
\end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

319 Where the two functions $f_1(\vartheta)$ and $f_2(\vartheta)$ are mutually exclusive. To evaluate $f_1(\vartheta)$ we first have to calculate
320 the integration limits $r_{\min}(\vartheta)$ and $r_{\max}(\vartheta)$:

$$\begin{aligned}
321 \quad & r_{\min}(\vartheta) = \max(0, r' - r_2) = 0 \quad \text{if} \quad r' < r_2 \\
& r_{\max}(\vartheta) = \min(r_1, r' + r_2) = r_1 \quad \text{if} \quad r_1 < r' + r_2
\end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

322 The first of Eq. (37) is always true if $r' < r_2$, because in this case $r' - r_2 < 0$. The second of Eq. (37) is always
323 true if $r_1 < r' + r_2$. We must consider different cases based on the relationships between r_1 , r_2 , and r' :

324 • **Case 1:** $r_1 \leq r_2$ and $r' \leq r_2 - r_1$

325 There are no intersections between the circles, hence $f_1(\vartheta) \neq 0$ and $f_2(\vartheta) = 0$. In this case $r_{\min}(\vartheta) = 0$
326 because $r' \leq r_2 - r_1 \Rightarrow r' < r_2$ and $r_{\max}(\vartheta) = r_1$ because $r_1 \leq r_2 \Rightarrow r_1 < r' + r_2$.

327 • **Case 2:** $r_1 > r_2$ and $r' \leq r_1 - r_2$

328 There are no intersections between the circles, hence $f_1(\vartheta) \neq 0$ and $f_2(\vartheta) = 0$. In this case $r_{\min}(\vartheta) = 0$
329 because $r' \leq r_1 - r_2 < r_2$ if $r_2 < r_1 < 2r_2$, and $r_{\max}(\vartheta) = r_2$ because $r' \leq r_1 - r_2 \Rightarrow r_1 \geq r' + r_2$.

330 • **Case 3:** $|r_1 - r_2| < r' \leq r_1 + r_2$

331 There are intersections between the circles, hence $f_1(\vartheta) = 0$ and $f_2(\vartheta) \neq 0$. In this case, if r' is sufficiently
332 small we have $r' - r_2 < 0$ and so $r_{\min}(\vartheta) = 0$ and $r_{\max}(\vartheta) = r_1$.

333 Hence, we have

$$334 \quad f_1(\vartheta) = 2\pi \int_0^{r_{\max}(\vartheta)} r dr = \begin{cases} \pi r_1^2 & \text{for } r_1 \leq r_2 \quad \text{and} \quad r' \leq r_2 - r_1 \\ \pi r_2^2 & \text{for } r_1 > r_2 \quad \text{and} \quad r' \leq r_1 - r_2 \end{cases} \tag{38}$$

335 and

$$336 \quad f_2(\vartheta) = \int_0^{r_1} 2r \arccos\left(\frac{r^2 + r'^2 - r_2^2}{2r r'}\right) dr \quad \text{for} \quad |r_1 - r_2| < r' \leq r_1 + r_2 \tag{39}$$

337 Using the substitution $\xi = r' \zeta$ and $\eta = \frac{r_2}{r'}$ in Eq. (39), we get:

$$338 \quad f_2(\vartheta) = r'^2 \int_0^{\frac{\eta}{r'}} 2\zeta \arccos\left(\frac{\zeta^2 + 1 - \eta^2}{2\zeta}\right) d\zeta \quad (40)$$

339 Now we are in the position to use formula 35 of [2]:

340

$$341 \quad \int 2\zeta \arccos\left(\frac{\zeta^2 + 1 - \eta^2}{2\zeta}\right) d\zeta = \zeta^2 \arccos\left(\frac{\zeta^2 + 1 - \eta^2}{2\zeta}\right) + \eta^2 \arccos\left(\frac{\eta^2 + 1 - \zeta^2}{2\eta}\right) - \zeta \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\zeta^2 + 1 - \eta^2}{2\zeta}\right)^2}$$

$$342 \quad \text{Using } \zeta = \frac{\xi}{r'} \Rightarrow d\zeta = \frac{1}{r'} d\xi$$

$$343 \quad f_2(\vartheta) = r'^2 \int_0^{\frac{\eta}{r'}} 2\xi \arccos\left(\frac{\xi^2 + r'^2 - \eta^2 r'^2}{2\xi r'}\right) d\xi = \quad (41)$$

$$= \left[\xi^2 \arccos\left(\frac{\xi^2 + r'^2 - r_2^2}{2\xi r'}\right) + r_2^2 \arccos\left(\frac{r_2^2 + r'^2 - \xi^2}{2r_2 r'}\right) - r' \xi \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{\xi^2 + r'^2 - r_2^2}{2\xi r'}\right)^2} \right]_0^{\eta/r'}$$

344 Substituting Eq. (38) and Eq. (41) into Eq. (36) we get:

$$345 \quad \int_{G_1} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta d\vartheta r dr d\phi d\psi = \int_{\vartheta_{\min}}^{\vartheta_{\max}} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta \cdot f(\vartheta) d\vartheta$$

346 with

$$347 \quad f(\vartheta) = \begin{cases} \pi r_1^2 & \text{for } r_1 \leq r_2 \quad \text{and} \quad r' \leq r_2 - r_1 \\ \pi r_2^2 & \text{for } r_1 > r_2 \quad \text{and} \quad r' \leq r_1 - r_2 \\ r_1^2 \arccos\left(\frac{r_1^2 + r'^2 - r_2^2}{2r_1 r'}\right) + r_2^2 \arccos\left(\frac{r_2^2 + r'^2 - r_1^2}{2r_2 r'}\right) - r' r_1 \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{r_1^2 + r'^2 - r_2^2}{2r_1 r'}\right)^2} & \text{for } |r_1 - r_2| < r' \leq r_1 + r_2 \end{cases} \quad (42)$$

348 Hence, recalling Eq. (16), we finally have:

$$349 \quad n(E_p, E_n) = 2N \cdot \sigma(E_n) \cdot \frac{dR(E)}{dE} \Big|_{E=E_p} \cdot \int_{\vartheta_{\min}}^{\vartheta_{\max}} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta \cdot f(\vartheta) d\vartheta \quad (43)$$

350 which is identical to Eq. (36) and (37) of [2]. To validate Eq. (43), and assess its agreement with numerical
 351 methods, we performed a full Geant4 Monte Carlo simulation. The simulation (G4, version 11.1.1) utilized
 352 the physics list FTFP_BERT_HP for robust neutron transport and the G4EmStandardPhysics_option4 for
 353 proton energy loss and electromagnetic interactions. The simulation reproduces an almost monoenergetic 2.45
 354 MeV neutron beam (mimicking the one of FNG, see [19]) impinging perpendicularly onto a polyethylene
 355 (G4_POLYETHYLENE) radiator slab, with material parameters equal to those already described in Ch. 5.
 356 The foil thickness was varied between 5 and 100 μm (mg/cm^2 equivalent) to study energy-loss effects. The
 357 source uniformly irradiated the foil surface, and recoil protons were tracked through the converter and into the
 358 telescope, where a downstream silicon detector (G4_Si, 300 μm thickness) served as a sensitive volume for
 359 energy deposition and counting efficiency. The simulation geometry exactly reproduces the on-axis converter–
 360 detector configuration of the analytical model for equal radii $r_1 = r_2$ by modeling both the radiator and the
 361 active detector surface as squares with lateral dimensions of 0.5 cm. The fixed distance between them
 362 corresponds to five times the radius ($d=2.5$ cm in the figure's context). The collimator, implemented as a

363 stainless-steel grid with 0.5 cm diameter holes, is correctly positioned relative to the detector and radiator. The
 364 recoil proton energy was calculated by the total energy deposition in the silicon detector volume. A total of 6
 365 $\times 10^9$ primary neutrons were simulated to ensure adequate statistics. The ordinate represents the normalized
 366 response function $n(E_p, E_n)$, per unit energy and per emitted neutron. The obtained spectral shapes (Fig. 8)
 367 show very good agreement with Eq. (43) across the tested thickness range, confirming the validity of the
 368 analytical formulation of [2] and the correctness of the implemented Bragg–Kleeman energy-loss model in
 369 this energy range.

No. of protons (1/MeV/source)

370

371 *Fig. 8 Comparison between Geant4 simulations (points) and Eq. (43) for 5 different density thicknesses (TPE) of a Polyethylene*
 372 *converter. The neutrons energy was almost monochromatic at 2.45 MeV and $r_1 = r_2 = 0.5$ cm, $d = 2.5$ cm, and 6×10^9 primary*
 373 *neutrons were used*

374

375 8 Closed-Form Solution for Equal-Radius Converter and Detector

376 Assuming the same radius r for the converter and the detector, one must work with the complete set of
 377 geometric constraints, as given in Eqs. (23) –(28). One must integrate the “good geometry” response over the
 378 converter’s surface. In the general case, the response is given by an expression of the form, see Eq. (16):

$$379 \quad n(E_p, E_n) = 2N \cdot \sigma(E_n) \cdot \left. \frac{dR(E)}{dE} \right|_{E=E_p} \cdot \int_{\vartheta_{\min}}^{\vartheta_{\max}} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta \cdot f(\vartheta) d\vartheta \quad (44)$$

380 The integration in Eq. (44) is performed over the polar angle ϑ , which is measured from the foil’s normal. In
 381 our setup, only the protons that exit the foil in the forward direction (i.e., toward the detector) contribute. This
 382 “forward hemisphere” corresponds to polar angles between 0 and $\pi/2$. Equation (42), for $r_1 = r_2 = r$, becomes:

$$383 \quad f(\vartheta) = 2r^2 \arccos\left(\frac{d \cdot \tan(\vartheta)}{2r}\right) - d \cdot \tan(\vartheta) r \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{d \cdot \tan(\vartheta)}{2r}\right)^2} \quad \text{for } 0 < d \cdot \tan(\vartheta) \leq 2r \quad (45)$$

384 We now substitute Eq. (45) into Eq. (44) to obtain a closed-form expression for the response function. The
 385 derivation proceeds through the following steps.

386 In the expanded form of Eq. (44), via the definition of $f(\vartheta)$, the innermost integration is over the azimuthal
 387 angle φ , with limits $\pm\varphi_{\max}(\vartheta, r)$ determined by the intersection of the converter and detector projections (Eq.
 388 (29)). For the equal-radius case $r_1 = r_2 = r$, the φ -integration in the last factor of Eq. (44) acts on a geometric

389 kernel that, after expressing the projected overlap in polar coordinates, takes the form $\int_0^{\varphi_{\max}} \sqrt{r^2 - r'^2 \sin^2 \varphi} d\varphi$
 390 , where $r' = d \cdot \tan(\vartheta)$ is the radial offset of the projection center on the detector plane. Factoring out r from
 391 the square root, the integrand becomes $r\sqrt{1 - (r'/r)^2 \sin^2 \varphi}$. Defining the elliptic modulus as
 392 $k = r' / r = (d / r) \tan(\vartheta)$, this integral is recognized as $r \cdot E(\varphi_{\max}, k)$, where
 393 $E(\varphi_{\max}, k) = \int_0^{\varphi} \sqrt{1 - k^2 \sin^2 t} dt$ is the incomplete elliptic integral of the second kind, expressed here in terms
 394 of the modulus k . In the closed-form results, the elliptic integrals are instead written using the name convention
 395 $\text{EllipticE}[\varphi, m]$, where the second argument is the elliptic parameter $m = k^2$. In particular, the final expressions
 396 involve the parameter $m = 1 + 4r^2/d^2$, which always exceeds unity; the elliptic integrals therefore become
 397 complex-valued, and the $\text{Im}[\dots]$ operation extracts the imaginary part to yield the physical result. The
 398 remaining integrations over r and ϑ can then be carried out analytically, yielding the full closed-form
 399 expression. Three distinct regimes arise depending on the value of ϑ : (i) $\vartheta \rightarrow 0$, where the detector projection
 400 is centered and the elliptic modulus $k \rightarrow 0$, leading to an indeterminate form that is resolved by taking the
 401 limit; (ii) intermediate ϑ , where $E(\varphi_{\max}, k)$ is evaluated directly; and (iii) $\vartheta \rightarrow \vartheta_{\max}$, corresponding to the
 402 boundary of the integration domain where $\varphi_{\max} \rightarrow \pi$ and the incomplete elliptic integral reduces to the complete
 403 elliptic integral $E(k)$. These cases are treated separately below. Carrying out this procedure, Eq. (44) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \int_{\vartheta_{\min}}^{\vartheta_{\max}} \sin \vartheta \cos^2 \vartheta \cdot \left(2r^2 \arccos\left(\frac{d \cdot \tan(\vartheta)}{2r}\right) - d \cdot \tan(\vartheta) r \sqrt{1 - \left(\frac{d \cdot \tan(\vartheta)}{2r}\right)^2} \right) d\vartheta = \\
 & \left[\frac{1}{6} r \cos(\vartheta)^2 \left(\begin{aligned} & -4r \operatorname{arcsec}\left(\frac{2r \cot(\vartheta)}{d}\right) \cos(\vartheta) + d \sqrt{\frac{d^2 + 4r^2 - d^2 \sec^2(\vartheta)}{r^2}} \sin(\vartheta) + \\ & 4d \operatorname{EllipticE}\left[\arcsin\left[\sqrt{\cos^2[\vartheta]}\right], 1 + \frac{4r^2}{d^2}\right] \sqrt{\frac{d^2 + 4r^2 - d^2 \sec^2[\vartheta]}{r^2}} \sin[\vartheta] \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{\sqrt{1 + \left(-1 - \frac{4r^2}{d^2}\right) \cos^2[\vartheta]} \cdot |\sin[2\vartheta]|}{\sqrt{1 + \left(-1 - \frac{4r^2}{d^2}\right) \cos^2[\vartheta]} \cdot |\sin[2\vartheta]|} \right) \right]_{\vartheta_{\min}}^{\vartheta_{\max}} \quad (46)
 \end{aligned}
 \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

405 Where with the notation $\text{EllipticE}[\phi, m]$ we have indicated the elliptic integral of the second kind (where the
 406 second argument is the parameter $m = k^2$) $E(\phi | m) = \int_0^{\phi} \sqrt{1 - m \sin^2 x} dx$. Now suppose that $\tau_3 \leq \tau_0$, hence from
 407 Eq. (33) we have $\vartheta_{\min} = 0$. Hence, Eq. (46) becomes (applying Eq. (33)):

$$\left[F(r, d, \vartheta) \right]_0^{\vartheta_{\max}} = \begin{cases} F(r, d, \vartheta_1) - F(r, d, 0) & \text{for } \vartheta_1 \leq \vartheta_2 \\ F(r, d, \vartheta_2) - F(r, d, 0) & \text{for } \vartheta_1 > \vartheta_2 \end{cases} \quad (47)$$

409 Hence, to calculate Eq. (47) we need to evaluate $F(r, d, \vartheta)$ for $\vartheta_1 = \arctan\left(\frac{2r}{d}\right)$, $\vartheta_2 = \arccos\sqrt{\frac{E_p}{E_n}}$ and for
 410 $\vartheta = 0$. The two cases in Eq. (47) are separated by a characteristic proton energy. Setting $\vartheta_1 = \vartheta_2$ and using
 411 $E_p = E_n \cos^2 \vartheta$ together with $\cos^2\left(\arctan\left(2r/d\right)\right) = d^2 / (d^2 + 4r^2)$ yields:

412

413

$$E_p^* \equiv E_n \cdot \frac{d^2}{d^2 + 4r^2} \quad (48)$$

414

415

416

417

418

Physically, E_p^* is the proton energy at which the kinematic emission cone just fills the geometric acceptance cone. For $E_p \leq E_p^*$ the kinematic cone is wider than the detector acceptance, so the geometric bound \mathcal{G}_1 limits the integration (the full converter–detector overlap contributes). For $E_p > E_p^*$, kinematics restricts protons to a narrower cone, $\mathcal{G}_2 < \mathcal{G}_1$, and only part of the detector is illuminated. The two conditions in Eq. (47), by taking \tan of both sides (monotonic), squaring and rearranging, using Eq. (48) can then be expressed as

419

$$\arctan\left(\frac{2r}{d}\right) \leq \arccos\left(\sqrt{\frac{E_p}{E_n}}\right) \Leftrightarrow E_p \leq E_p^*$$

$$\arctan\left(\frac{2r}{d}\right) > \arccos\left(\sqrt{\frac{E_p}{E_n}}\right) \Leftrightarrow E_p > E_p^*$$

420

Since some parts may assume complex values, we must always ensure that we take the real part.

421

- When $\mathcal{G}_{\max} = \mathcal{G}_1$ we get an indeterminate form of type 0 / 0 because $\sqrt{\frac{d^2 + 4r^2 - d^2 \sec(\mathcal{G})^2}{r^2}} \rightarrow 0$,

422

and $\sqrt{1 + \left(-1 - \frac{4r^2}{d^2}\right) \cos(\mathcal{G})^2} \rightarrow 0$. Anyway, taking the limit from below of \mathcal{G} to \mathcal{G}_1 it's easy to check

423

that $F(r, d, \mathcal{G}_1)$ is equal to 0.

424

- When $\mathcal{G}_{\max} = \mathcal{G}_2$, calculating $F(r, d, \mathcal{G})$ in Eq. (47) is straightforward.

425

- When $\mathcal{G} = 0$, we get an indeterminate form of type 0 / 0, but it can be reduced to (again, taking the real part only):

426

427

$$F(r, d, 0) = -\frac{1}{3} \left(\pi r^2 - d^2 \operatorname{Im} \left[\operatorname{EllipticE} \left(1 + \frac{4r^2}{d^2} \right) \right] \right) \quad (49)$$

428

where with the notation $\operatorname{EllipticE}(k)$ we have indicated the complete elliptic integral of the second kind

429

(again with the parameter $m = k^2$) $E(m) = E\left(\frac{\pi}{2} | m\right)$. Hence, we have that Eq. (47), using Eq. (48) can be

430

written as (considering only the real part):

431

$$n(E_p, E_n) = 2N \cdot \sigma(E_n) \cdot \frac{dR(E)}{dE} \Big|_{E=E_p} \cdot \frac{1}{3} \cdot \begin{cases} T_0 & \text{Case1: if } E_p \leq E_p^* \\ T_1 + T_2 + \frac{T_3}{D} + T_4 & \text{Case2: if } E_p > E_p^* \end{cases} \quad (50)$$

432

where:

$$\begin{aligned}
T_0 &= \pi r^2 - \text{Im} \left[d^2 \text{EllipticE} \left[1 + \frac{4r^2}{d^2} \right] \right] \\
T_1 &= \pi r^2 + \frac{1}{2} d \sqrt{\frac{(E_n - E_p) E_p (d^2 (-E_n + E_p) + 4E_p r^2)}{E_n^3}} \\
T_2 &= -2 \left(\frac{E_p}{E_n} \right)^{3/2} r^2 \text{ArcSec} \left[\frac{2r}{d \sqrt{-1 + \frac{E_n}{E_p}}} \right] \\
T_3 &= d^2 \sqrt{d^2 (-E_n + E_p) + 4E_p r^2} \text{EllipticE} \left[\arcsin \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{\frac{E_n}{E_p}}} \right], 1 + \frac{4r^2}{d^2} \right] \\
D &= \sqrt{d^2 (E_n - E_p) - 4E_p r^2} \\
T_4 &= -d^2 \text{Im} \left[\text{EllipticE} \left[1 + \frac{4r^2}{d^2} \right] \right]
\end{aligned}$$

433

434 Figure 9 shows Eq. (50) for six (r, d) pairs spanning the range $r/d = 6$ to $r/d = 1/6$, with $E_n = 12$ MeV. The red
435 dashed line marks the kinematic-geometric transition E_p^* , which separates the two cases in Eq. (50): Case1 (
436 $E_p \leq E_p^*$) geometry-limited; Case2 ($E_p > E_p^*$) kinematics-limited. Three distinct regimes are visible:

- 437
- 438 • For $r \gg d$ (panels $r = 6, d = 1$ and $r = 5, d = 2$), the transition energy E_p^* is much smaller than E_n , so
439 Case 2 applies over nearly the full E_p range. The response is a smooth, nearly symmetric bell curve,
440 peaked at intermediate E_p .
 - 441 • For $r \ll d$ (panels $r = 2, d = 5$ and $r = 1, d = 6$), E_p^* is close to E_n . Case 1 — in which the integration
442 covers the full geometric domain — dominates up to E_p^* , so the response grows only via the rising
443 dR/dE factor until the kinematic cutoff kicks in. This produces the classic 'shark-fin' shape of the
444 idealized monoenergetic response, with the characteristic sharp drop at $E_p \rightarrow E_n$.
 - 445 • For $r \sim d$ (panels $r = 4, d = 3$ and $r = 3, d = 4$), the transition falls in the middle of the plotted range,
and the response is asymmetric.

446 The closed form Eq. (50) therefore continuously interpolates between these regimes. Realistic PRT
447 configurations with point sources on axis, small source-detector distance relative to the detector radius, and
448 energy loss in the converter ($r > d$) produce bell-curve responses in this idealized limit; the additional 'shoulder'
449 seen in full numerical simulations (e.g. Fig. 3) arises from off-axis and finite-geometry contributions beyond
450 the equal-radius, on-axis assumption.

451

452 *Fig. 9 Response function $n(E_p, E_n)$ from Eq. (50) for six (r, d) pairs (in cm) at $E_n = 12$ MeV. The vertical red dashed line marks the*
 453 *kinematic–geometric transition E_p^* : the Case1 branch of Eq. (50) applies for $E_p \leq E_p^*$ (left of the line), the Case2 branch for $E_p > E_p^*$*
 454 *(right of the line).*

455 This derived analytical solution advances the field by providing a closed-form expression for the PRT response
 456 function $n(E_p, E_n)$ for the equal-radius converter/detector on-axis geometry, accounting for energy losses due
 457 to a finite converter thickness. It's a fully analytical formulation that enables precise, rapid calculation of the
 458 response function across the full range of equal-radius geometries — from bell-curve responses at small d/r to
 459 shark-fin responses at large d/r — without relying on computationally intensive numerical methods.

460

461 9 Conclusions

462 The recent analytical description of the PRT response functions has a long history, beginning with the general
 463 approach of [1] and the integral formalism of [2]. These classical treatments express the detector response as
 464 multidimensional integrals over geometric and energy-loss variables and were later implemented numerically
 465 or through series expansions. Subsequent works occasionally reduced certain geometric integrals to elliptic-
 466 type forms for specific configurations. Yet, the results were generally evaluated numerically rather than written
 467 in closed analytical form. More recent studies, e.g., [20], [21] and [22], likewise rely on numerical or Monte-
 468 Carlo evaluations of the same underlying integrals. To the authors' knowledge, Eq. (50) represents the first
 469 compact closed-form expression in terms of complete elliptic integrals that fully describes the PRT response
 470 for the equal-radius, on-axis geometry, including proton energy-loss effects. Earlier works either omitted
 471 energy-loss corrections, treated unequal-radius geometries, or stopped at integral or series representations. The
 472 present formulation therefore extends the classical integral formalism to an explicit analytical solution,
 473 providing both physical transparency and a convenient benchmark for numerical and Monte Carlo methods.
 474 In a forthcoming study, the validity of the newly derived Eq. (50) will be examined through an independent

475 computational verification that integrates the analytical response function with a B-spline-based unfolding
476 framework, allowing a quantitative assessment of its accuracy against synthetic data and benchmark
477 simulations.

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479 References

- 480 [1] K. Weise, “Die antwortfunktion von ruckstossprotonen-teleskopen,” *NUCLEAR INSTRUMENTS*
481 *AND METHODS*, vol. 67, pp. 197–204, 1968.
- 482 [2] H. Gotoh, H. Yagi, and Y. Harayama, “Calculation of the response function of semiconductor proton
483 recoil counters with a radiator of finite thickness,” *NUCLEAR INSTRUMENTS AND METHODS*, vol.
484 109, pp. 349–353, 1973.
- 485 [3] E. Amaldi, D. Bocciarelli, and G. C. Trabacchi, “On proton-neutron collision. I,” *Ricerca Scientifica*,
486 vol. 12, pp. 830–842, 1941.
- 487 [4] S. J. Bame Jr., E. Haddad, J. E. Perry Jr., and R. K. Smith, “Absolute Determination of
488 Monoenergetic Neutron Flux in the Energy Range 1 to 30 Mev,” *Review of Scientific Instruments*,
489 vol. 28, no. 12, pp. 997–1006, Dec. 1957, doi: 10.1063/1.1715824.
- 490 [5] T. Nakamura, “Angular Distribution of n-p Scattering at 14.1 MeV,” *J Physical Soc Japan*, vol. 15,
491 no. 8, pp. 1359–1366, 1960, doi: 10.1143/JPSJ.15.1359.
- 492 [6] J. Konijn, A. Lauber, B. Tollander, and N. (Sweden) AB Atomenergi, “Calculations of Total and
493 Differential Solid Angles for a Proton Recoil Solid State Detector,” 1963.
- 494 [7] H. Gotoh and H. Yagi, “The detection efficiency and the response function of semiconductor proton
495 recoil counters with axial symmetry to a point neutron source,” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods*,
496 vol. 101, no. 2, pp. 395–396, 1972, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0029-554X\(72\)90215-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0029-554X(72)90215-7).
- 497 [8] K. Kovačević *et al.*, “Use of photodiodes for neutron dosimetry,” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods*,
498 vol. 148, no. 2, pp. 291–298, 1978, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0029-554X\(70\)90181-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0029-554X(70)90181-3).
- 499 [9] L. Ruby, “Further comments on the geometrical efficiency of a parallel-disk source and detector
500 system,” *Nucl Instrum Methods Phys Res A*, vol. 337, no. 2, pp. 531–533, 1994, doi:
501 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-9002\(94\)91124-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0168-9002(94)91124-X).
- 502 [10] D. J. Thomas and E. J. Axton, “The need for a relativistic approach when calculating proton recoil
503 telescope efficiencies,” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods*, vol. 174, no. 1, pp. 321–322, 1980, doi:
504 [https://doi.org/10.1016/0029-554X\(80\)90448-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0029-554X(80)90448-6).
- 505 [11] S. Ghodke, S. V. Y. Singh, and S. Santra, “Efficiency calculation of proton recoil neutron telescope
506 with relativistic correction for neutron energy 4 to 20 MeV,” *Applied Radiation and Isotopes*, vol.
507 184, p. 110171, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apradiso.2022.110171>.
- 508 [12] W. Ulmer, “Theoretical aspects of energy–range relations, stopping power and energy straggling of
509 protons,” *Radiation Physics and Chemistry*, vol. 76, no. 7, pp. 1089–1107, 2007, doi:
510 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radphyschem.2007.02.083>.
- 511 [13] R. Zhang, P. J. Taddei, M. M. Fitzek, and W. D. Newhauser, “Water equivalent thickness values of
512 materials used in beams of protons, helium, carbon and iron ions,” *Phys Med Biol*, vol. 55, no. 9, pp.
513 2481–2493, 2010, doi: 10.1088/0031-9155/55/9/004.
- 514 [14] Y.-S. Park and J.-H. Kim, “Proton Beam Energy Determination Using a Device for Range
515 Measurement of an Accelerated High Energy Ion Beam,” *Journal- Korean Physical Society*, vol. 59,
516 no. 22, pp. 679–685, 2011, doi: 10.3938/jkps.59.679.

-
- 517 [15] N. Tsoulfanidis and S. Landsberger, *Measurement and Detection of Radiation*. Boca Raton: CRC
518 Press / Taylor & Francis, 2015.
- 519 [16] A. N. Caruso, “The physics of solid-state neutron detector materials and geometries,” *Journal of*
520 *Physics: Condensed Matter*, vol. 22, no. 44, p. 443201, 2010, doi: 10.1088/0953-8984/22/44/443201.
- 521 [17] C. Ham *et al.*, “A Design and its Validation of a Proton Recoil Telescope with a Silicon Detector for
522 Measurements of Fast Neutrons,” *Journal of the Korean Physical Society*, vol. 73, no. 3, pp. 271–
523 277, 2018, doi: 10.3938/jkps.73.271.
- 524 [18] J. B. Marion and J. L. Fowler, *Fast Neutron Physics*. Interscience Publishers, 1963.
- 525 [19] A. Pietropaolo *et al.*, “The Frascati Neutron Generator: A multipurpose facility for physics and
526 engineering,” *J Phys Conf Ser*, vol. 1021, p. 012004, May 2018, doi: 10.1088/1742-
527 6596/1021/1/012004.
- 528 [20] N. L. Snidow and H. D. Warren, “Wall-Effect Corrections in Proportional Counter Spectrometers,”
529 *Nuclear Instruments and Methods*, vol. 51, p. 109, 1967, doi: 10.1016/0029-554X(67)90172-4.
- 530 [21] A. Manna and et al., “A Proton Recoil Telescope for the Characterisation of the Neutron Beam at
531 n_TOF,” in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Nuclear Data for Science and*
532 *Technology (ND2019)*, 2019.
- 533 [22] C. Chatel, P. Marini, and et al., “Experimental Validation of the Gaseous Proton Recoil
534 Telescope (GPRT) for Quasi-Absolute Neutron Flux Measurements,” *EPJ Web Conf*, 2024.